

ISic1306

I.Sicily inscription 1306

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 242

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. · Θ(εοῖς) · Κ(αταχθονίοις) ·
2. Κασσία Βενοῦστα ἔ
3. ζησεν ἔτη · ἔνδεκα
4. μῆνες θ ἡμέρες · η ·
5. πατήρ καὶ μήτηρ τέ
6. κνω γλυκυτάτῳ ἐποίησαν

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

To the subterranean divinities. Kassia Benousta, lived for 11 years, 9 months, and 8 days. Her father and mother built this for their sweetest child.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492911

EDCS 39101676

PHI 140798

PHI 316210

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0483 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 67

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